

Research On The Path Of High-Quality Development Of Modern Higher Vocational Education Under The Background Of High Technology

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Abstract

One of the most important trends in the development of vocational courses is that higher vocational courses institutions are becoming more international in scope. When it comes to internationalizing China's higher vocational courses, there are both opportunities and challenges. This study, which takes use of computer-aided technology, is the first to assess the importance of globalization in higher vocational courses.

Introduction

Lifelong learning has become more widely accepted in the knowledge economy thanks to the "Internet+" background that has emerged since the Internet era, according to Hu (2020). People have expressed greater interest in vocational courses as a universal public resource that can be accepted by all citizens. Aside from its obvious advantage in cultivating technical skills, vocational course's on-the-job training and post career education stages remain woefully underdeveloped. The Internet's inherent open and distance learning characteristics, on the other hand, can help teachers of vocational courses overcome space constraints, expand the scope of vocational courses, and keep pace with technological advancements.

Before and after students enter the workforce, vocational courses refers to activities that aim to help students acquire specific professional knowledge, attitudes or abilities as well as develop good professional ethics or discipline in order to be prepared for the responsibilities of their chosen profession (Du, 2021). Vocational education, which encompasses college education, higher vocational courses, and adult higher education, is an essential part of our country's education system.. It's a kind of educational development tasked with cultivating future leaders for the benefit of society and the economy. In addition, China's vocational courses system, which is a kind of educational growth, encompasses both higher vocational courses and higher education.

Vocational education and distance education can successfully interact and collaborate because of the relevance and flexibility of vocational courses and the openness and universality of distance education. As a technique, means, and strategy, several scholars have urged that in-depth vocational courses be integrated with remote vocational courses (Ling et al, 2021). Teachers and students from all over the globe benefit from this global dissemination of the greatest ideas and technologies in vocational courses and distant learning. This opens up new opportunities for interdisciplinary collaboration, practice integration, community service, and personal growth. It is necessary to analyze the integration route, research technique, and procedure for the integration of distance and open education with vocational training.

I. Research Objectives

This study will assess the high-quality development of vocational courses under the background of high technology while determining the level of higher teacher professional development and internalization as mediated by *construction of modern vocational courses system*, which thus serves as a basis for a high-quality development of vocational courses program.

This research will answer the following specific question:

1. What is the level of assessment of internalization of higher vocational courses?
2. How do the respondents perceive the high-quality development of vocational courses under the background of high technology in terms of:
 - a. higher teacher professional development
 - b. Internationalization
 - c. *construction of modern vocational courses system*
3. Do the following variables predict the high-quality development of vocational courses under the background of high technology?
 - a. higher teacher professional development
 - b. Internationalization
 - c. *construction of modern vocational courses system*
4. Does internalization predicts high-quality development of vocational courses?

II. Significance of the Study

As a broad word for the rules and regulations that govern educational institutions, they are referring to the system of educational norms that are established at all levels. Institutions that implement education and those that oversee education are both participating in this endeavor. Each educational subsystem and the way it functions are both topics of interest to the discipline known as "mechanism" studies. Educational systems and mechanisms act as safety nets to keep students from engaging in non-standard behaviors while also helping to guarantee that education runs as smoothly as possible.

For the vocations taught in vocational courses, a large number of highly skilled, high-quality professionals are needed. Convergence may be observed when it comes to culture's aims. ' Vocational education should adapt to the changing requirements of society and the economy, and the skills that are developed should be in line with the demands of the labor market, the needs of the workplace, and the advancement of society and the economy as a whole.

As outlined above, the purpose of vocational courses is to cultivate technical skills that are both highly skilled and of the highest professional quality, as well as to cultivate technical skills that are both highly skilled and of the highest quality, as defined above. As well as a high degree of humanity, they should also have solid scientific basic theoretical knowledge and professional capabilities, among other traits. Developing a professional job after completing a vocational courses program is a dynamic and ongoing process that must keep pace with changes in the vocational area, postsecondary skill renewal, and the ever-changing standards of professional excellence. At the same time, new industries will arise and outdated technologies and roles will be phased out as a consequence of the continuing adjustment and regeneration of the industrial structure.

III. Related Literature

The Chinese government unveiled a blueprint for a new vocational courses system. An open vocational courses system in China would encourage higher vocational schools to host high-level Sino-foreign cooperative education projects and institutions, which would have a positive impact on the entire nation. Internal needs and developments in the sphere of higher vocational courses have placed globalization on top of the list. In order for China's vocational colleges to become world-class, the country will implement an international school operating system that is in-depth, multi-form, and all-around. When it comes to recruiting new students, approaches like "going out" and "inviting in" will become more popular as higher education becomes more globally oriented. Professionals with advanced degrees will be able to move about more easily, making international migration of this kind more common. Higher vocational courses will be able to expand its reach and distribution channels by delivering staff training services. The "student crisis" that comes with a "cliff drop" will be lessened as a consequence. By experimenting with the open education style of teaching, higher education institutions will foster global competence in accordance with regional standards (Outline of the National Medium- and Long-Term Talent Development Plan, 2010).

The globalization of educational institutions has a direct impact on the development of international skills. Since this is the current and long-term goal of the institution, higher vocational schools must cultivate an

international teaching staff with a global perspective. Higher vocational teachers' professional growth is a continuous and dynamic process. Students at technical colleges and universities should have access to ongoing classroom instruction and hands-on training opportunities. Because of their dedication to the continuous improvement of teaching, research, service, and management, higher vocational colleges will progressively grow their quality and soft power. Due to education's expanding global reach, higher vocational educators' worldviews may be widened as a consequence. The use of worldwide teaching methods, curriculum development, and teaching standards will be encouraged at higher vocational institutions. This will lead to a rise in the professional development of instructors in higher education (MoE, 2011).

When it comes to one's professional development, one must constantly evaluate one's ability to adapt to the ever-changing nature of one's job responsibilities. In order to enter the workforce, students must have some type of education or training prior to enrolling in college. Vocational education should adapt to the changing requirements of society and the economy, and the skills that are developed should be in line with the demands of the labor market, the needs of the workplace, and the advancement of society and the economy as a whole. There are several micro-level aspects of vocational courses that aim to build students' professional qualities while also honing their vocational skills in order to get them ready for the workforce. With this, distant and open education's aims of talent development may be achieved by integrating both growth routes (MoE, 2015).

When it comes to open education management, administrators and teachers should work together to increase standards. Several initiatives are being conducted to raise standard management and service awareness and to enhance the organization of instruction, administration of courses, assessment of courses and teaching support services even further. It is essential that the online course's evaluation and incentive methods be improved, along with the course's instructional design. Plan and execute innovative online teaching activities that encourage instructor-student connection in a variety of forms while strengthening the overall stability of the teaching staff. They'll devote more effort to developing, co-constructing, and implementing educational resources. Search for and include new instructional resources, as well as keep existing ones up-to-date and optimized, in order to make them more useful (TSC, 2019).

Open and semi-open examinations for provincially operated courses will be widened to include more courses and the style and discipline of tests will be bolstered in order to improve social repute and public trust.

As outlined above, the purpose of vocational courses is to cultivate technical skills that are both highly skilled and of the highest professional quality, as well as to cultivate technical skills that are both highly skilled and of the highest quality, as defined above. As well as a high degree of humanity, they should also have solid scientific basic theoretical knowledge and professional capabilities, among other traits. Students who have received their secondary education through a system of vocational instruction enter the workforce with the knowledge that their professional careers are in a state of flux and must adapt to the ever-changing demands of their respective fields, their postsecondary education, and the evolving standards of professionalism (Hou, 2010).

The globalization of China's Higher Vocational Education will gain traction by establishing a team of academics with a global outlook, and this will be critical to the process. Consequently, they must devote all of their resources to the "talent introduction" program. The establishment of a "talent introduction" project fund will be used to attract globally extraordinary experts, technologists, front-line teachers, and other professionals. In light of the increase in the number of local teachers, more restrictions on foreign instructors' ability to teach in the country may be put in place. China's vocational courses system must adhere to standard management standards in order to assure the admittance of foreign teachers. International colleges and universities will have the opportunity to learn from our instructors if they make our teaching, scientific research, and technological innovation clearly visible. If they work together on collaborative teaching, they may increase the resources available to vocational college teachers for international research, training, and exchange. These steps will help to increase the number of foreign teachers in the United States.

IV. Research Methodology

This study is a survey research that has been designed into a descriptive -correlational. Descriptive method consists in measuring a variable or a set of variables as they naturally exist (Gravetter and Forzano, 2016). A descriptive design is used to answer research questions one to four. The stats that in correlational design two or more variable are correlated with the use of one or more correlation coefficients. In addition, the moderated-mediation approach is used to find the indirect effect of saving behavior and personal profile of the respondents. It is based on the objective which seeks to find the effect of internalization of higher vocational courses and high-quality

development of vocational courses under the background of high technology on their higher teacher professional development as intervened by Internationalization and moderated by construction of modern vocational courses system.

This is a quantitative research which use parametric inferential to study linear causality among the variable and develop a good fit program for high-quality development of vocational courses under the background of high technology for university teachers in China. Large sample size was used and data was collected from universities, then analysis to give impartiality and validity on the proposed program.

This research is based on moderated mediation. Moderation and mediation model is used when an indirect effect is moderated, that is the indirect effect varies across levels of the moderator. Mediation and moderation methods are frequently used statistical methods in the social, health science, behavioral as well as business, medicine and others areas of study (Hayes, 2017).

Moderated Mediation

Moderated mediation occurs when the strength of an indirect effect of an independent variable to a dependent variable via a mediator variable depends on the level of fourth variable.

Figure 1. A general moderated mediation model that shows mediator variable, M_i linking the independent variable, X , and the dependent variable, Y . Also, shown is the moderator, W

The regression equations for a moderated mediation are as follows;

$$M_i = i_1 + a_1X + a_2W + a_3XW + r$$

$$Y = i_2 + b_1M'_i + b_2XWM'_i + c_1X + c_2W + c_3XW + r_2$$

Where X is the independent variable, Y the dependent variable, W the moderator, M_i the mediator, the product of XW denotes the W interaction of X on M_i ; also, the Product XWM_i represents the interaction between X , W and M_i (Hayes, 2007; Wu & Zumbo, 2007). Also, i_1 and i_2 are regression intercepts, a_1 , a_2 , a_3 , b_1 , b_2 , c_1 , c_2 , and c_3 are regression coefficients of their corresponding terms, and r_1 and r_2 are residuals. As implied in McKinnon (2008), b_2 represents the moderated mediation effect.

Statistical diagram

Figure 2. Statistical diagram

Conditional indirect effect of X on Y through $M_i = (a_{1i} + a_{3i}W) (b_{1i} + b_{3i}W)$ Direct effect of X on Y = c'

Mediation and Moderation analysis are procedures that give researchers more understanding about a causal relationship between two major variable that is being influenced by some other variable(Wu & Zumbo, 2007). Mediation occurs when the effect of a predictor variable on a dependent variable is coursed through a third variable (Edwards & Lamber, 2007). The third variable is called the mediator variable. The regression equations for a mediation model can be expressed as

$$M_i = a_0 + a_1X + a_2W + a_3XW$$

$$Y = b_0 + b_1M_i + b_2X + b_3W + b_4M_iW$$

Where X is the predictor or independent variable, Y the dependent Variable, and M_e the mediator, i_1 and i_2 are intercepts and r_1 and r_2 are regression residuals; a represents the relationship between X and M_e , b the relationship between M_e and Y and c' the relationship between X and Y (Preacher, Rucker, & Hayes, 2007). Specially, a is the slope coefficient of M_e and X, respectively. In addition, the coefficient a and b express the presence, strength and significance of the indirect effect of X on Y through M_e (Preacher, Rucker and Hayes, 2007, p. 188). According to Mackinnon et al. (2007), if they let C denote the direct effect of X on Y (i.e. in the absence of M_e), then the indirect effect is usually expressed as $c-c'$ which equivalent to ab .

On the other hand, moderation takes place “when the effect of an independent variable on a dependent variable varies according to the level of a third variable which interacts with the independent variable” (Edwards and Lambert, 2007). This third variable is called a moderated variable . In other words, an independent variable alters the strength variable and the direction of the relationship between independent variable and dependent variable (Preacher, Rucker & Hayes, 2007, Wu & Zumbo, 2007). The regression equation for moderation is presented as follow

$$Y = C_0 + C_1X + C_2W + C_3XW + C_4XW^2 + C_5W^2$$

Where X represent the independent variable, Y the dependent Variable, and M_o the Moderator, I represents the intercept, a, b, and c are the coefficient of Y regression on X, interaction between X and M_o and demotes the Moderation effect.

V. Results and Analysis

I. Assessment of internalization of higher vocational courses

Table 1. Assessment of internalization of higher vocational courses

Indicators	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean
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VE1=I have the ability to deal with high quality development of higher education	1082	1.00	4.00	2.9723
VE2=I have the understanding to deal with high quality development of higher education	1082	1.00	4.00	2.9880
VE3=I am knowledgeable about vocational courses	1082	1.00	4.00	3.0074
VE4=I have well understanding about vocational courses	1082	1.00	4.00	2.9482
VE5=I spend a lot of time thinking about the significance of vocational courses	1082	1.00	4.00	3.0499
VE6=I try to stay informed about vocational courses	1082	1.00	4.00	2.7763
VE7=I have the ability and understanding to vocational courses	1082	1.00	4.00	2.7532
VE8=I am easily able to keep track of development of vocational courses under the background of high technology	1082	1.00	4.00	2.7542
Internalization	1082	1.11	4.00	2.9061

Table 1 represents the level of significance of internalization of higher vocational courses of the respondents. The highest indicator was “I spend a lot of time thinking about the significance of vocational courses” with weighted mean of 3.07 verbally interpreted as “High.” The lowest indicator was “I have the ability and understanding to vocational courses” with weighted mean of 2.75 verbally interpreted as “High” also. Overall, the composite weighted mean was 2.92 and verbally interpreted as “High.”

Vocational education in China is now being globalized with vigor and commitment. Certain sectors are missing, making them wary of entering the global market with Chinese companies. It is true that Chinese vocational courses concepts, teaching courses, teaching achievements, and technological innovation have been transmitted internationally through cooperation and exchange, but there are still some outstanding contradictions and problems in the international development of Chinese vocational courses, particularly when it comes to teacher training and the teaching profession.

II. Assessment of the Higher Teacher Professional Development

Table 2. Assessment of the Higher Teacher Professional Development

Indicators	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean
HTPD1=The development of international skills is inextricably linked to the globalization of instructors.	1081	1.00	5.00	1.8807
HTPD 2=Higher vocational institutions must develop an international teaching staff with a worldwide perspective and awareness, which is both the present duty and the long-term objective	1081	1.00	5.00	1.6957

HTPD 3=Higher vocational instructors' professional development is an ongoing and dynamic process. Higher vocational institutions must offer ongoing education and practice possibilities.	1081	1.00	5.00	1.7909
HTPD 4=Higher vocational colleges will steadily increase their quality and soft power via continual development in teaching, research, service, and management. Internationalization of education has the potential to broaden the worldwide perspective of higher vocational instructors.	1082	1.00	5.00	1.8198
HTPD 5=Higher vocational colleges will enhance teachers' professional research and cutting-edge trends via the use of international teaching models, curriculum development, and teaching standards, which will raise the degree of professional development of higher vocational teachers	1081	1.00	5.00	1.7354
Higher Teacher Professional Development	1082	1.00	5.00	1.77821

Table 2 represents the assessment of the higher teacher professional development of the respondents. The highest indicator was “The development of international skills is inextricably linked to the globalization of instructors” with weighted mean of 1.88 verbally interpreted as “Poor” The lowest indicator was “Higher vocational institutions must develop an international teaching staff with a worldwide perspective and awareness, which is both the present duty and the long-term objective” with weighted mean of 1.69 verbally interpreted as “Very Poor” also. Overall, the composite weighted mean was 1.77 and verbally interpreted as “Very Poor.”

There is a serious shortage of high-quality teachers at vocational institutions, especially those that must fulfill academic education criteria. The absence of adequate financing for vocational courses has resulted in lower pay for instructors than for regular high school teachers. It's also challenging to attract and maintain high-quality teachers and other staff members since vocational courses is seen as a second-class school. As a result of increasing private investment, vocational schools may be able to partially relieve this problem.

In order to recruit the best instructors, they feel that partnering with companies to promote academic and general knowledge rather than industrial and vocational skills is the best option. Academic teaching at technical institutions may benefit greatly from university and high school professors and teachers. This is a way to take advantage of China's high-quality educational materials. When local business leaders donate their time to their children's schools,

they not only help build deeper linkages between their companies and universities, but they also provide an additional motivation for schools to seek out and keep on board top-notch educators and students.

III. Assessment on the Internationalization of the Respondents

Table 3. Assessment on the Internationalization of the Respondents

Indicators	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean
I1=There is a general lack of understanding about resource mobilization.	1080	1.00	5.00	1.8157
I2= Lack of a strong feeling of internalization	1080	1.00	5.00	1.5759
I3= Weak international idea	1081	1.00	5.00	1.5597
I4= Disagreements and difficulties in the field of international development	1082	1.00	5.00	1.4030
I5= International activities are limited.	1082	1.00	5.00	1.6275
I6= International school operating system that is in need of improvement	1080	1.00	5.00	1.6139
Internationalization	1082	1.00	4.90	1.5992

Table 3 represents the assessment on the internationalization of the respondents. The highest indicator was “There is a general lack of understanding about resource mobilization” with weighted mean of 1.81 verbally interpreted as “Low” The lowest indicator was “Disagreements and difficulties in the field of international development” with weighted mean of 1.40 verbally interpreted as “Very Low” also. Overall, the composite weighted mean was 1.59 and verbally interpreted as “Very Low”

China's foreign environment is becoming more and more complex. In today's competitive environment, opportunities and challenges coexist in every facet of society. China's vocational schools should lead the way in this area. With frequent updates on how to operate an educational institution, China's higher vocational colleges can develop a solid foundation for running a school, which will help their respective nations become more globalized. Teaching, scientific research, and administration all fall under the umbrella of school administration. Vocational schools should focus on both the global and national markets, and have a full grasp of both. To keep up with the rising demand for vocational training, it's important to make sure that programs are aligned with international best practices. By actively adopting globally advanced techniques, China's vocational courses will continue to expand and innovate. This will lead to an improvement in teaching methods, quality of instruction and evaluation methods and instruments..

IV. Assessment on the construction of modern vocational courses system

Table 4. Assessment on the construction of modern vocational courses system

Indicators	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean
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CMVE1= The globalization of higher vocational courses has risen to the top of the list of internal demands and growth trends in the field.	1081	1.00	5.00	1.5125
CMVE2=The techniques will be promoted as a result of the internationalization of higher vocational courses.	1081	1.00	5.00	1.6772
CMVE3=High skilled talents will be able to travel more freely, and international migration of high skilled workers will become the rule rather than the exception.	1082	1.00	5.00	1.6044
CMVE4=By providing staff training services, higher vocational courses will be able to extend the scope and distribution channels of higher vocational courses.	1076	1.00	5.00	1.6468
CMVE5=China will develop a world-class vocational college via an in-depth, multi-form, and all-round international school operating system, which will improve the core competitiveness of China's vocational colleges.	1079	1.00	5.00	1.6237
CMVE6=Building an open vocational courses system in China would encourage higher vocational schools to high-level cooperative education projects and institutions, which will benefit the whole country.	1081	1.00	5.00	1.6216
Construction of modern vocational courses system	1082	1.00	5.00	1.6143

Table 5 represents the construction of modern vocational courses system. The highest indicator was “The techniques will be promoted as a result of the internationalization of higher vocational courses.” with weighted mean of 1.67 verbally interpreted as “Very Poor.” The lowest indicator was “The globalization of higher vocational courses has risen to the top of the list of internal demands and growth trends in the field.” with weighted mean of 1.51 verbally interpreted as “Very Poor” also. Overall, the composite weighted mean was 1.61 and verbally interpreted as “Very Poor.”

It's possible to take courses in anything from business and computer science all the way up to fashion design and automobile repair at vocational institutions. However, the demand for a particular course is one factor that most individuals examine before enrolling in that course. When it comes to a student's ability to adapt his or her knowledge and skills to the changing demands of the labor market, neither vocational institutions nor students understand this. As an alternative, they advocate for hybrid classes that combine instruction with independent research. There is still a lot of "academic" and "generic" content in the vocational school curriculum. Research efforts may also play an important role in vocational courses, and technical invention and innovation are part of the responsibility of vocational schools.

V. **Regression –Predictors of high-quality development of vocational courses under the background of high technology**

Table 5. Regression –Predictors of high-quality development of vocational courses under the background of high technology

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	higher teacher professional development	.	Stepwise (Criteria: Probability-of-F-to-enter <= .050, Probability-of-F-to-remove >= .100).
2	Internationalization	.	Stepwise (Criteria: Probability-of-F-to-enter <= .050, Probability-of-F-to-remove >= .100).

a. Dependent Variable: high-quality development of vocational courses under the background of high technology

Table 5 represents the Regression –Predictors of high-quality development of vocational courses under the background of high technology. It shows that higher teacher professional development and Internationalization can be variables under the predictors of high-quality development of vocational courses under the background of high technology.

Table 6
Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.474 ^a	.225	.224	.43592	.225	312.682	1	1080	.000
2	.505 ^b	.255	.253	.42754	.030	43.740	1	1079	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), higher teacher professional development

b. Predictors: (Constant), higher teacher professional development, Internationalization

Table 6 represents the model summary in predicting the predictors for high-quality development of vocational courses under the background of high technology.

Table 7
ANOVA

	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	59.417	1	59.417	312.682	.000 ^b
	Residual	205.227	1080	.190		
	Total	264.645	1081			
2	Regression	67.413	2	33.706	184.398	.000 ^c
	Residual	197.232	1079	.183		
	Total	264.645	1081			

a. Dependent Variable: high-quality development of vocational courses under the background of high technology.

b. Predictors: (Constant), higher teacher professional development

c. Predictors: (Constant), higher teacher professional development, Internationalization

Table 7 represents the model for regression residual between the higher teacher professional development (.000<.05) and Internationalization (.000<.05). It shows that both predictors were significantly different with the high-quality development of vocational courses under the background of high technology.

Table 8
Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	1.206	.079		15.337	.000		
higher teacher professional development	.468	.026	.474	17.683	.000	1.000	1.000
2 (Constant)	1.051	.081		13.044	.000		
higher teacher professional development	.470	.026	.476	18.099	.000	1.000	1.000
Internationalization	.091	.014	.174	6.614	.000	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: high-quality development of vocational courses under the background of high technology.

Table 8 represents the model for constant between the higher teacher professional development (.000<.05) and Internationalization (.000<.05). It shows that both predictors were significantly related with the high-quality development of vocational courses under the background of high technology.

Table 9
Excluded Variables^a

Model	Beta In	t	Sig.	Partial Correlation	Collinearity Statistics		
					Tolerance	VIF	Minimum Tolerance
1 construction of modern vocational courses system	.160 ^b	6.062	.000	.181	.999	1.001	.999
higher teacher professional development	.166 ^b	6.318	.000	.189	.999	1.001	.999

	Internationalization	.174 ^b	6.614	.000	.197	1.000	1.000	1.000
2	construction of modern vocational courses system	.036 ^c	.669	.504	.020	.244	4.101	.244
	Internationalization	.052 ^c	.850	.396	.026	.188	5.330	.188

a. Dependent Variable: high-quality development of vocational courses under the background of high technology.

b. Predictors in the Model: (Constant), higher teacher professional development

c. Predictors in the Model: (Constant), higher teacher professional development, Internationalization

Table 9 represents the excluded variables for construction of modern vocational courses system (.181>0.05) higher teacher professional development (.189>0.05) and Internationalization (.197>0.05). It shows that predictors were not significantly related with the high-quality development of vocational courses under the background of high technology.

VI. Mediation Effect of higher teacher professional development and Internationalization On high-quality development of vocational courses

Table 10. Mediation Effect of higher teacher professional development and Internationalization On high-quality development of vocational courses

Items	Correlation	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Internationalization ->high-quality development of vocational courses	0.161	7.445	0
higher teacher professional development ->high-quality development of vocational courses	0.542	26.908	0

Table 10 represents the mediation effect of effect of higher teacher professional development and internationalization on high-quality development of modern higher vocational courses. The results revealed that the indirect and total effect of higher teacher professional development ($\beta = 0.161$, $t = 7.445$, $p = 0.00$) and Internationalization ($\beta = 0.542$, $t = 26.908$, $p = 0.00$) on high-quality development of vocational courses was not significant. This means that high-quality development of vocational courses with the inclusion of grit does mediate on the relationship of higher teacher professional development and Internationalization.

VII. Moderate The Effect of higher teacher professional development and Internationalization On high-quality development of vocational courses

Table 11. Moderate The Effect of higher teacher professional development and Internationalization On high-quality development of vocational courses

Items	t-value	p-Value new
Internationalization ->high-quality development of vocational courses	3.861	0.981
higher teacher professional development ->high-quality development of vocational courses	8.231	0

Moderation analysis on the effect of higher teacher professional development and Internationalization On high-quality development of vocational courses in terms of higher teacher professional development that as mediated by grit, on the relationship by Internationalization showed that ($t = 3.861$, $p = 0.981$).

VI. Summary and Conclusions

Summary

The level of assessment of internalization of higher vocational courses of the respondents shows the highest indicator was “I spend a lot of time thinking about the significance of vocational courses” with weighted mean of 3.07 verbally interpreted as “High.” The lowest indicator was “I have the ability and understanding to vocational courses” with weighted mean of 2.75 verbally interpreted as “High” also. Overall, the composite weighted mean was 2.92 and verbally interpreted as “High.”

The assessment of the higher teacher professional development of the respondents shows the highest indicator was “The development of international skills is inextricably linked to the globalization of instructors” with weighted mean of 1.88 verbally interpreted as “Poor” The lowest indicator was “Higher vocational institutions must develop an international teaching staff with a worldwide perspective and awareness, which is both the

present duty and the long-term objective” with weighted mean of 1.69 verbally interpreted as “Very Poor” also. Overall, the composite weighted mean was 1.77 and verbally interpreted as “Very Poor.”

The assessment on the internationalization of the respondents shows the highest indicator was “There is a general lack of understanding about resource mobilization” with weighted mean of 1.81 verbally interpreted as “Low” The lowest indicator was “Disagreements and difficulties in the field of international development” with weighted mean of 1.40 verbally interpreted as “Very Low” also. Overall, the composite weighted mean was 1.59 and verbally interpreted as “Very Low”

The construction of modern vocational courses system shows the highest indicator was “The techniques will be promoted as a result of the internationalization of higher vocational courses.” with weighted mean of 1.67 verbally interpreted as “Very Poor.” The lowest indicator was “The globalization of higher vocational courses has risen to the top of the list of internal demands and growth trends in the field.” with weighted mean of 1.51 verbally interpreted as “Very Poor” also. Overall, the composite weighted mean was 1.61 and verbally interpreted as “Very Poor.”

The Regression –Predictors of high-quality development of vocational courses under the background of high technology shows that higher teacher professional development and Internationalization can be variables under the predictors of high-quality development of vocational courses under the background of high technology. The model for regression residual between the higher teacher professional development (.000<.05) and Internationalization (.000<.05) and shows that both predictors were significantly different with the high-quality development of vocational courses under the background of high technology. The model for constant between the higher teacher professional development (.000<.05) and Internationalization (.000<.05) shows that both predictors were significantly related with the high-quality development of vocational courses under the background of high technology.

The excluded variables for construction of modern vocational courses system (.181>0.05) higher teacher professional development (.189>0.05) and Internationalization (.197>0.05) shows that predictors were not significantly related with the high-quality development of vocational courses under the background of high technology.

The mediation effect of effect of higher teacher professional development and internationalization on high-quality development of modern higher vocational courses. The results revealed that the indirect and total effect of higher teacher professional development ($\beta = 0.161$, $t = 7.445$, $p = 0.00$) and Internationalization ($\beta = 0.542$, $t = 26.908$, $p = 0.00$) on high-quality development of vocational courses was not significant. This means that high-quality development of vocational courses with the inclusion of grit does mediate on the relationship of higher teacher professional development and Internationalization.

Moderation analysis on the effect of higher teacher professional development and Internationalization On high-quality development of vocational courses in terms of higher teacher professional development that as mediated by grit, on the relationship by Internationalization showed that ($t = 3.861$, $p = 0.981$).

Conclusions

There are many important causes for the absence of academic instruction at vocational schools, which may be described in the following ways: In addition to a lack of financial investment from society and a high level of government involvement, curricula lack academic flexibility, students are divided into different school types primarily on the basis of their entrance exam scores, and vocational schools are treated as second-class institutions. Vocational schools are suffering from a scarcity of qualified professors and instructors.

Several proposals have been presented in order to address the aforementioned problem. Reduce the involvement of the government by developing hybrid curricula and implementing technical research projects; offering vocational school graduates an appealing option to continue their education at a university level; emphasizing general and academic knowledge over industry and vocational skills by aligning academic institutions and businesses.

People's living standards are rising as a result of the fast growth of human society in the modern era, as well. Because of this, individuals are more concerned with education, and the overall level of education in the nation is growing as a result. As a result, China's educational development policy should be revised in order to keep up with the globalization trend in higher education. Vocational courses in China will be transformed into a new educational idea as a result of the integration of the building of the one belt, one road initiative. In order to

compete with the "one belt, one road" initiative, they must establish an international talent training system. Developing worldwide skills at Higher Vocational Colleges via systematic inventive thinking should be encouraged, with a range of computer technologies being used as an auxiliary learning tool. Higher vocational schools must take advantage of this possibility. By placing a high value on the development of international talents, they can create a top-level design, curriculum system, and campus activities that will serve as the foundation of an international talents development program.

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